

Mid-term assessment of the implementation phase

Intermediate assessment of the implementation phase including impact and updated risk-register

D1.4

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EPOS brings together European nations and combines solid Earth science infrastructures and their capital of human expertise, data, and services into one integrated system for a better understanding of planet Earth dynamics

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SUMMARY

This document presents the Mid-Term Assessment of the EPOS IP project, which is deliverable D1.4 scheduled at M24 of the project lifetime.

We report on the status of the EPOS IP project at the end of the first two years planned to be dedicated to the implementation of services from a technical, legal, governance and financial point of view. This document also describes the strategy for assessing the impact and includes an update of the risk register.

Four strategic activities characterize the EPOS IP project and we detail achievements and results for each of them: Implementation of TCS and ICS from a technical, legal, governance and financial point of view, Harmonization with national strategies and priorities, Communication with stakeholders, Management and coordination with the EPOS-ERIC legal establishment.

The EPOS IP project has submitted to the EC its first Scientific and Technical Periodic Report scheduled at M18. This report (for the period M1-18) has been approved by the European Commission. The present document contains an update of the M18 EC scientific report, but it is structured to summarize the achievements following the project concept and strategic work plan.

INTRODUCTION

The EPOS Implementation Phase is composed of the EPOS IP project and the legal establishment of EPOS-ERIC, both identified as strategic actions to move EPOS toward its operational phase. EPOS IP project has the overarching objective of implementing the services and building the new infrastructure. Its timeline covers a 4 years' time span (see Figure 1) through the following phases: the TCS-ICS integration and technical development (2 years), the TCS-ICS validation (1 year) and the Pre-operational phase (1 year).

Figure 1. In the EPOS IP project, three check points during the project time have been designed preceding the pre-operational phase planned for the fourth year of activity:

- i. at the end of Year 1 of EPOS IP, consisting of a preliminary overview of the implementation of Thematic Core Services (TCS) and Integrated Core Services (ICS) to assess their progress (taking into account legal, governance, financial, and technical issues) and their scientific relevance to EPOS. This allowed for the finalization of the EPOS business plan, the TCS Cost Book as well as for the identification of the Data, Data-products, Software and Services (DDSS), now summarized in the DDSS Master Table. This also allowed for the management of risks verifying mitigation actions and contingency plans.
- ii. at the end of the Year 2, aimed at identifying those DDSS elements that will enter into the one-year Validation Phase, starting in October 2017. This second check is referred to as the **Technical Readiness Assessment**.
- iii. at the end of the Year 3, consisting of an assessment of progresses and impact to validate the maturity of DDSS elements (together with their Service Providers) to enter in the pre-operational phase in October 2018 (Year 4). This will be the completion of the Validation Phase. It is expected that during Year 3 of the EPOS IP project, the EPOS-ERIC will enter into force.

The following key actions characterize the EPOS IP work plan:

- Implementation of TCS and ICS from a technical, legal, governance and financial point of view
- Harmonization with national strategies and priorities
- Communication with stakeholders
- Management and coordination with the EPOS-ERIC legal establishment.

These actions have been foreseen in the EPOS IP proposal as depicted below in Figures 2 and translated into the project concept (Figure 3). The service implementation activities concern the contributions from Thematic Core services (WPs 8 to 17) and transversal WPs dealing with legal and governance (WP4), financial (WP5), ICS implementation (WP7) and interoperability (WP6). Harmonization with national strategies and priorities is coordinated by WP3, while communication with stakeholders by WP2. Finally, activities dealing with management and coordination with the EPOS-ERIC legal establishment are coordinated by WP1.

Figure 2. EPOS IP project EPOS workflow in the four main activity areas: Management, Harmonisation, Communication and Service Implementation, showing its relation with decision flow.

Figure 3. The EPOS IP project's concept and approach.

1. KEY OBJECTIVES AND THEIR CURRENT RELEVANCE

The overarching goal of the enterprise as a whole is to bring together European nations and combine solid Earth science infrastructures and their capital of human expertise, data, and services into one integrated system for a better understanding of planet Earth dynamics.

In particular, the EPOS IP project work plan has been designed to achieve the following key objectives:

1. *Implementing thematic services (TCS) for the diverse communities contributing to EPOS;*
2. *Ensuring TCS integration within the full EPOS delivery framework, covering legal, governance and financial aspects, and technical connection to ICS;*
3. *Developing the ICS to provide interoperability, data management and access to services;*
4. *Creating optimal conditions for the central coordination of the EPOS-ERIC (Executive Coordination Office and ICS Central Hub);*
5. *Ensure long-term financial & legal sustainability for EPOS-ERIC and implemented services;*
6. *Harmonizing the EPOS implementation with national priorities and strategies;*
7. *Further gaining users' trust and awareness of the impact of the new research exploitation platform;*
8. *Integrating EPOS in the global science community to enhance the EPOS services;*
9. *Fostering training, outreach and international cooperation.*

These objectives are synergetic and coherent with the establishment of the EPOS-ERIC. They have been proved to be appropriate and effective to maintain the planned roadmap and timeline and we confirm their relevance to the purpose of the EPOS initiative in general and IP project in particular. The adopted risk management plan and risk register have been, of course, updated during the last two years to monitor the progress and the feasibility of the EPOS implementation phase. More in general, we can confirm that also the EPOS IP project's concept, decision flow, and work flow has been proved to be appropriate and effective to the coordination and management of the work plan.

To support the above statements, we provide concrete examples on how EPOS addressed its specific challenges in the past 24 months:

1. Implementing thematic services (TCS) for the diverse communities contributing to EPOS

The Thematic Core Services have been engineered bottom up, taking into account the requirements and requests of the involved communities, both scientists and IT experts. The work done so far for the technical implementation of data and services includes:

- elaboration of the Data, Data-products, Service and Software provision (DDSS Master table), currently containing 384 elements of which 125 declared ready for validation within the project
- implementation of the Metadata catalogue for TCS interoperability with ICS
- design of the user interface and user registry for the ICS and TCS
- harmonization of data standards and quality management across communities
- design of the service portfolio for developing new services within TCS taking advantage of e-science innovation
- launch of the Technical Readiness Assessment (internal validation).

2. Ensuring TCS integration within the full EPOS framework, covering legal, governance and financial aspects, and technical connection to ICS

To guarantee the provision of data and services (DDSS), TCS need to adopt an effective internal structure to be legally and financially linked to EPOS-ERIC and technically compatible with ICS-C as well as a shared governance ensuring representativeness for the broad community for each field of solid Earth science included in EPOS. To address this,

- each TCS is establishing an appropriate legal and governance structure represented by a Consortium Agreement to ensure the engagement of the communities and national teams
- each TCS has identified Service Providers (SP) which are legal entities in charge of delivering the DDSS and coordinating data management and integration by signing Service Contracts with EPOS-ERIC; the necessary legal contracts have been drafted and agreed within the involved communities
- General Principles of Data Policy and Access Rules have been agreed within communities and approved by BGR, and the roadmap for their application to DDSS elements has been designed.
- clear TCS cost categories have been identified to enable EPOS-ERIC to fund the TCS operation and maintenance (i.e. Governance, Community-Coordination, Outreach, TNA, support of operation, maintenance and upgrading of services).

3. Developing the ICS to provide interoperability, data management and access to services

The work done for the technical implementation of ICS includes:

- implementation of the Metadata catalogue for interoperability
- design of the user interface and user registry for the ICS and TCS
- design of the ICS central hub and development of its prototype
- design of the service portfolio for developing procurement policies to access computational resources
- selection of the countries that will host the ICS Central hub, namely: UK, France and Denmark.

4. Creating optimal conditions for the central coordination of the EPOS-ERIC (Executive Coordination Office and ICS Central Hub)

The progress achieved on structuring the Governance of TCS as well as the delivering of the TCS Cost Book and the EPOS Financial Plan has contributed to achieve pivotal results for EPOS:

- also thanks to the convincing business plan of EPOS, the Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR) has unanimously approved the Statutes and the Scientific and Technical Description and eleven countries have officially endorsed the Step 1 submission of EPOS-ERIC
- the definition of the legal framework, in terms of data policies & access rules and consortium agreements & service contracts, created the conditions for designing the EPOS-ERIC operational phase.

5. Ensure long-term financial & legal sustainability for EPOS-ERIC and implemented services

EPOS IP has elaborated a projection of operation costs detailed for the 98 TCS services currently included in the TCS Cost Book and for the operations of the ECO and ICS-C. The validation plans for these projections concern two timeframes, one preceding the start of EPOS-ERIC operations, the other during the first 5 years of EPOS operations. Before EPOS-ERIC begins, the TCS Cost Book will be the reference document on operational costs. The total costs add up to approximately 15 M€ per year for the entire TCS data and service provision plus 1.3 M€ for Trans-National Access. The costs of the ECO and the ICS-C correspond to about 2,5 M€ that will be mainly covered by the host premium, leaving only 0,40 M€ on the ERIC budget.

These figures represent the costs of the EPOS overall delivery framework assuming that all the services in the Cost Book will be operational at the end of EPOS IP project. However, it is anticipated that the validation of services starting in 2017 will lead to a time-diluted activation of EPOS services during the first five years of EPOS-ERIC. As the validation of services progresses in EPOS IP, it will be possible to draw some projections of the annual operational costs for the validated services. The finalization of the TCS Cost Book has fostered the implementation of the EPOS business plan, a standalone document that describes the envisaged financial framework for the delivery of EPOS services.

6. Harmonizing the EPOS implementation with national priorities and strategies

The outcome of the harmonization work is corroborated by:

- EPOS is included in the national roadmap of 12 countries
- national consortia or joint research units have been created in additional 16 countries
- currently, data providers belong to 138 research organizations and 256 research infrastructures distributed within 25 countries and 5 international organizations (Orfeus, EMSC, EUREF, INTERMAGNET, EuroGeoSurveys).

7. Further gaining users' trust and awareness of the impact of the new research exploitation platform

EPOS user community primarily comes from the thematic communities (TCS) participating to the integration plan, but it is not limited to the EPOS IP partnership because users also come from:

- the international organizations participating in EPOS
- global initiatives participated by the engaged RIs (e.g. FDSN in seismology, GEO supersites for volcano and near-fault observatories, INTERMAGNET for geomagnetism)

To attract and engage these scientific users as well as other users from different stakeholder categories (private sector, governmental agencies, students), EPOS is counting on its service provision in terms of integration of data, metadata and services at the EPOS and on the efficiency of its Communication Plan. The establishment of national consortia and joint research units, with a relevant number of contributing organizations to EPOS IP, also corroborates this achievement.

8. Integrating EPOS in the global science community to enhance the EPOS services

EPOS is involved at different levels in many RIs and international projects at global scale, thus contributing in creating the collaborative framework necessary for the sharing of scientific results and observational data. In particular, collaborations with the following initiatives have been strengthened and/or established:

- EPOS is a GEO (Group of Earth Observation) participating organization;
- Geo-Hazard Supersite coordinated by GEO;
- Global Earthquake Model, collaborating for developing seismic hazard products for Europe;
- US initiatives funded by NSF, such as IRIS (seismology), UNAVCO (geodesy) and EarthCube (integrated e-infrastructures), collaborating on data sharing and management;
- AuScope in Australia and Chykviiu and E-Defense in Japan;
- RDA, EarthCube, GEOSS, collaborating for ICT innovation with e-science initiatives at global level.

9. Fostering training, outreach and international cooperation

The EPOS training strategy and consequent program require that the EPOS provision, if not fully operative, is at least partially implemented having clearly defined the services provided by the TCS and set up the ICS platform. For this reason, the launch of the training activities is scheduled in the third year of EPOS IP project, after the EPOS validation process of services has been performed. The first two years of the project has been therefore dedicated to design the training plan and to develop feasible strategies to engage users and stakeholders and trainers as well. In summary, the EPOS IP training activities will be performed in close cooperation with WP3, WP6 and WP7, and TCS WPs.

- Outreach towards potentially interested users of the TCSs services is achieved by EPOS participation to several events (e.g. EGU 2016 and 2017).
- EPOS newsletter (<https://www.epos-ip.org/news-press/epos-ip-newsletter>) has the aim of disseminating news, events and research developments relevant to the EPOS Community and the Solid Earth Science domain and beyond.
- In terms of global cooperation with projects, initiatives and infrastructures, shared initiatives and events were promoted with ENVRI Plus <http://www.envriplus.eu> (e.g. ENVRI week, ENVRI Community booth at EGU, etc.), VRE4EIC www.vre4eic.eu, EGI.ENGAGE https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/EGI-Engage:Main_Page, EUDAT www.eudat.eu, EOSC <https://eoscpilot.eu>, RDA Europe <https://europe.rd-alliance.org> and EMSO DEV www.emso-eu.org.

2. WORK PLAN IMPLEMENTATION

To tackle the challenge of building a Pan-European RI like EPOS combining many diverse disciplines in solid Earth science for creating a new approach to access data, data-products, services and facilities, we have designed the architecture following a clear scientific vision and mission that is currently implemented to build the novel infrastructure through sustainable technical, legal, governance and financial models. As described in the previous chapter, during the first 24 months of the EPOS IP project the work plan has been carried out coherently with the roadmap to address the EPOS key objectives. Importantly, all the deliverables planned to be prepared within M24, both the 70 to be uploaded on the Participant Portal and the 65 internal (uploaded on the Intranet area) have been completed; they all have been delivered on time with the only exception of D4.2 and D17.2 whose delay has been justified to the Commission.

In this chapter we report in more details what accomplished in the framework of the four key actions that characterize the EPOS IP work plan (Figure 3), namely 1) Implementation of TCS and ICS from a technical, legal, governance and financial point of view, 2) Harmonization with national strategies and priorities, 3) Communication with stakeholders, 4) Management and coordination with the EPOS-ERIC legal establishment.

2.1 Implementation of TCS and ICS - technical, legal, governance and financial point of view

The **Implementation** of the Thematic Core Services (TCS) is carried out within the ten WPs (from WP8 to WP17, green vertical boxes in Figure 3). The TCSs have been designed during the Preparatory Phase taking into account the requirements of the different EPOS communities and currently represent the collaborative framework where to achieve implementation. Each TCS is organized to provide specific services to users through single or distributed infrastructures and it is composed of existing services and data infrastructures adapted for integration in EPOS as well as new services as identified by the community as key for future Earth science research. Full implementation of the services will be achieved only by working at the same time on shared **technical solutions** to implement the data infrastructures and the web services, a **governance structure** to coordinate, manage and orchestrate data and community services as well as formal links to the EPOS managing bodies, a **financial plan** to guarantee the long-term sustainability of involved data- and e-infrastructures.

Concerning the **technical implementation**, the TCS WPs (from 8 to 17) are working in synergy with WP6 and WP7 (brown and green horizontal boxes, respectively in Figure 3) to guarantee the definition of standards and protocols as well as interoperability for the EPOS provision. Indeed, the main objective of WP6 and WP7 is to provide interactions between the Integrated Core Services (ICS) and the Thematic Core Services (TCS) to integrate the TCS data, data products, services and software (DDSS) into the ICS system and to ensure their interoperability through the Integrated Core Services Central Hub (ICS-C). This synergic approach will also deliver innovative solutions for data management, processing, preservation and deposition, including data traceability and user accountability. During the first two years of the project life requirements and use cases (RUC) from all the TCS WPs with regard to the implementation of EPOS ICS-C have been collected. This process has been carried out in five steps: 1) First round of RUC collection, 2) Second round of RUC collection, 3) ICS-TCS Integration Workshop, 4) Third round of RUC collection, 5) Implementation of RUC to the CERIF metadata. The first four steps were successfully conducted, the fifth step is already initiated and will continue in the following months. During these interactions (through interviews and videoconferences), each TCS WP has provided their priority list of data, data products, services and software (DDSS) and use case descriptions. The collected information is now kept in an MS-Excel file (DDSS Master Table) where the details of all DDSS elements are included. The initial number of 369 DDSS elements declared from the TCS WPs as potentially suitable for the EPOS provision has been reduced to 133 elements corresponding to those currently under implementation (columns green in Figure 4). A fraction of these, at M25, will be assessed ready for entering into the Validation Phase. The remaining DDSS elements are likely to require more time for implementation. The portioning of the DDSS elements with respect to the various TCS WPs, shows an uneven distribution, which reflects the nature of each TCS. Some of the multidisciplinary TCS have a large set of DDSS elements, whereas the disciplinary TCS have less DDSS elements. However, the disciplinary TCS have more standardized data when compared to the remaining TCS. These results should be considered in progress, and it is expected that changes will apply as the project progresses.

Figure 4. Level of maturity of the DDSS elements for each TCS WP as of M24 (after D6.1).

In the framework of the TCS DDSS provisions, an essential component to be considered is the **Data Management Plan** (DMP) because it secures the sustainability of these services in the long-run and provides a plan for integrating the technical issues of availability, access, storage, archiving and curation of DDSS provisions with the legal, governance and financial aspects. During the RUC collection process, initial information about the TCS level DMPs have been requested to TCS WPs by WP6. The results indicate a complex landscape, where some of the service providers have institutional DMPs, whereas almost none of the TCSs have a dedicated DMP, with the exception of the European or global level service providers such as ORFEUS, EMSC, INTERMAGNET etc. Each TCS WP has been therefore requested to map their internal status of DMPs, and develop a TCS level DMP combining these individual institutional DMPs. The collected DMPs will then make the background for developing a DMP at EPOS ICS level.

Contemporaneously with the technical implementation of Thematic Core Services (TCS), WP6 and WP7 jointly worked at developing the Integrated Core Services (ICS) and the ICS-C platform that will allow access to data, data products and services of the EPOS community. The initial prototype developed during the EPOS PP is now more sophisticated as it has been implemented in several dimensions: (i) the metadata catalog is more detailed and has a greater coverage of TCS assets, ICS-D and CES parameters; (ii) the AAI (Authentication, Authorisation, Accounting Infrastructure) has been defined related to the catalog and utilising the latest developments; (iii) after various experiments a development method for the GUI (Graphical User Interface) has been defined leading to a demonstration of this GUI utilising a prototype ICS-C system; (iv) associated with the GUI an API for programmatic access has been defined; (v) the initial definitions of the workflow manager have been defined; (vi) the initial definitions and design of the system manager have been defined; (vii) the potential message buses have been assessed and one chosen; (viii) early work has been done on the interfaces between ICS-C and both ICS-D and Computational Earth Science (CES). The new demonstrator will be presented to the community during the Validation workshop on October 2017. WP6 and WP7, following the developments on European ICT initiatives (e.g. EUDAT, EGI,

PRACE, etc.) and especially on European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative, also worked on designing ICS-D and interoperability with ICS-C. This is important, as the future ICS-D services will probably rely on the outcome of these initiatives. Currently, however, these initiatives are not yet mature to provide clear procurement policies, and hence it is difficult at this stage to start planning any integration to these future services.

In terms of **legal and governance**, each TCS, supported by the WP4 Team that provided common guidelines and models, have proposed its own legal and governance structure. Few interactions made both collegially among WP4 and all TCSs and between WP4 and each TCS singularly led to a design of the legal and governance structure, including a template Consortium Agreement, that will allow each TCS to have a stable governance and a smooth and transparent decision-making process while including all relevant services and data providers (legal entities and networks) as well as the user community in order to be able to decide on, oversee and check the quality and appropriateness of the service provision. In more details such a governance structure will: (i) allow for clear decision-making and management procedures, (ii) guarantee a long-term sustainability, (iii) enable the TCSs to enter into future service agreements with the EPOS-ERIC legal entity. WP4 then provided a metric for assessing the maturity and the progress of implementation of the governance. Furthermore, WP4, after discussion within the whole community, drafted a document on EPOS data policy and access rules to physical facilities, presently endorsed by TCSs and, importantly, by the Board of Governmental Representatives. A summary of these activities is described in D4.3 and D4.4 elaborated at M24.

The design of the Thematic Core Services (TCS) **financial framework** for the long-term EPOS operational phase is managed by WP5 by involving all TCS WPs. To ensure that the financial framework is coherent with the legal and governance structure which is an on-going activity that will be continued as the governance of the TCS progresses, WP5 is working in close collaboration with the WP4 Team. The geographical distribution of services and the coherency of the funding model with national priorities for hosting institutions is constantly verified by collaborating with the WP3 and WP6 and 7 teams. In particular, WP5 and WP6/7 have started to interact to harmonise the technical (DDSS Master Table) and financial (TCS Cost-book, see below) proposals. WP5 during the first 24 months of the project, defined a number of steps for achieving all these goals, from giving guidelines to the TCSs helping them to prepare a report on Financial Work and Sustainability for TCS Implementation to the definition of an adequate TCS cost structure model, the Assessment of TCS investment and maintenance costs (TCS Cost-book) and Proposed TCS funding model. Of particular importance is the EPOS Cost-book whose first version has been delivered in March 2017 after an iterative process held with the TCS during the first 18 months of EPOS-IP. As a result, it was possible to generate concrete figures regarding the potential dimension of the EPOS-ERIC catalogue of services (see D5.4). In summary:

- The DDSS (Data, Data Products, Services, Software) proposed by the TCS could be aggregated under services already developed or expected to be developed during the first 5 years of EPOS operations
- Those services included also governance, coordination and outreach services for each TCS
- Each service had a designated service provider, and 45 different identified services providers were identified in 18 countries

- Total yearly costs for the entire TCS provision were estimated in 15 M€, plus 1.3 M€ for transnational (physical) access to research infrastructures. This includes a 25% rate as indirect costs and 10% for upgrading of services
- The staff involved in delivering the catalogue was estimated in 110 FTE per year
- In terms of funding, approximately 75% of the costs would be covered at national level (institutes, national programs, etc.), and 25% would remain to be funded through country-level contributions to EPOS-ERIC (membership fees) or through other means

The TCS Cost-Book needs to be updated by the verification of proposed costs for services likely to enter in operation, i.e. after the validation process will end on September 2018. This will imply the confirmation of Service Providers for each TCS service as well as the confirmation of national funding by Service Providers.

2.2 Harmonization with national strategies and priorities

During the first 24 months EPOS IP, efforts on harmonization with national priorities have been carried on under the coordination of the WP3 Team who worked in close collaboration with the transversal WP6 *ICS-TCS Integration & Interoperability*, as well as with the WP2 Communication & Dissemination, WP4 Legal & Governance, and WP5 Finance. Specifically, the activities consisted of: i) a survey among members of the Board of National Scientific Representatives (BNSR) to collect information on national priorities, national roadmaps, national consortia, and national funding to the EPOS delivery framework, ii) an integrated analysis of National Roadmaps for Research Infrastructures at European level, evaluating their contents in terms of the relevance for the EPOS infrastructure, iii) a survey among the 20 EPOS Harmonization Groups (HGs) summarizing their current activities concerning access rules of relevance for drafting the General Principles for Trans-National Access (TNA). This allowed a thorough revision process with EPOS TCS planning to provide TNA through the EPOS TNA brokerage. After the revision, achieved approval on the TNA General Principles by the Service Coordination Board (SCB). Since then, a first TNA pilot case has already been conducted and reported by Utrecht University and GFZ Potsdam in the framework of WP16. An update on these issues are available in D3.1.

2.3 Communication with stakeholders

The range of communities participating in EPOS is a direct measure of its multidisciplinary breath and potential far-reaching impact on the Earth Science community. Nevertheless, this is not the limit of the EPOS ambition and vision. By enabling multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary research for a better understanding of the Earth's system, EPOS ambition is to help making a step change in developing new concepts and tools for key answers to scientific and socio-economic questions concerning geo-hazards and geo-resources as well as Earth science applications to the environment and to human welfare. To reach this goal EPOS has to communicate with very diverse stakeholders including solid Earth scientists but also scientists belonging to disciplines outside the solid Earth domain as well as government representatives, the private sector and, critically, society. For an efficient communication allowing for a clear and appropriate message accurately targeted within such a diverse reservoir, EPOS identified "target audiences" as reported in Table 1 (for more details, see the EPOS Communication Plan D2.1).

Table 1. Stakeholder's categories and target audiences in EPOS Implementation Phase.

Stakeholders' category		Target audience
I	Scientists	Data Providers
		Data users within the solid earth community
		Data users outside the solid earth community
		IT experts
II	Governments	National governments
		Funding agencies
		European commission
III	Private sector	Industry
		Small and Medium Enterprises (SME)
IV	Society	Students at any level
		General public

The identification of target audiences allows the realistic operation of the EPOS communication strategy by undertaking effective communication initiatives based on short- and mid-term purposes coherent with the communication objective of **effectively engaging with stakeholders**. Because different stakeholders have different levels of interest and influence to EPOS, we have adopted communication strategy and actions accordingly. During the Preparatory Phase we already mapped both the active interest of stakeholders in EPOS and the influence they had in the EPOS design and preparatory work. In the Implementation Phase, after having optimized the definition of the target audiences and the related communication strategy, EPOS is working to make such strategy efficient to ensure that the level of interest and influence of its stakeholders move towards the right-top corner of the diagram (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Stakeholder mapping at M24 of EPOS IP. In the bottom-right box, the situation during the EPOS PP is reported for comparison. Note: “Inform, Consult, Collaborate, Engage-Approve” represent subsequent evolution stages (phases) of communication; see Table 1 for colour code.

After almost two years in the Implementation Phase, we can update the “Stakeholder map” as follows:

- I. Scientists - Data providers and IT experts had and will continue to have a high active influence and interest in EPOS; Data Users within SES now have a much more active influence and interest whereas Users from outside SES still need to be involved in EPOS.
- II. Governments - National Governments and Funding Agencies moved into the engage-approve sector, thus significantly improving their influence on EPOS; EPOS is still (and will remain) in a collaborative framework with Civil Protection agencies.
- III. Private Sector remains mostly in the same position with a slightly more active interest if we consider the private data providers; EPOS just started its communication activities. As a propaedeutic action to plan forthcoming engagement strategies, EPOS performed a consultation intended to map the landscape of interactions with private sector within the EPOS communities. The questions have been addressed to the project partners and to the WP Leaders representing ten different TCSs. Over ten TCSs Communities, 80% of the partner organisations participating in the consultation declared their cooperation with large industries, and 70% of them detailed their collaboration with Small and medium-sized enterprises SMEs.
- IV. Society had a passive interest and influence on EPOS during the Preparatory Phase and it will most possibly remain in the same position for most of the Implementation Phase; nevertheless, the design and future launch of the EPOS training program already moved the student target audience toward the consult sector of the diagram indicating a much higher interest and influence of this stakeholder.

Moreover, EPOS has defined a timeline for reaching the defined target audiences as their contributions to the various EPOS development phases (namely conception, preparatory, implementation and operational phases) are different and will occur over different time spans. We believe each of them can be most effectively engaged at a different stage of the project lifetime. Figure 5 shows the updated timeline of EPOS interaction with the stakeholder’ categories. Once interaction is initiated, it is then continued for the rest of the project. EPOS IP has started the impact assessment of communication (D2.8) as a contribution to the overall impact assessment of the Implementation Phase.

Figure 6. Stakeholder interaction timeline. Note: “Inform, Consult, Collaborate, Engage, Approve” represent subsequent evolution stages (phases) of communication. Phases, as reported in this timeline, mean to indicate the highest-level reached for the corresponding category. For example, having put only the “Inform” phase on the stakeholder category Society, means that EPOS has not started any bi-lateral form of communication with this category (Society has a passive influence and interest in EPOS, see Fig. 2).

2.4 Management and coordination with the EPOS-ERIC legal establishment

The EPOS IP **Management** is under WP1 responsibility. The general purpose of management is to ensure a smooth implementation of the work plan by an efficient coordination of the activities foreseen in the different work packages – particularly those dedicated to Thematic Core Services (TCSs) implementation and dealing with the Integrated Core Services (ICS) development - optimizing and rationalizing the use of resources, enhancing the communication both among partners and with the European Commission, and ensuring the effective integration of project achievements with the strategic actions dedicated to the establishment of the EPOS-ERIC. A tangible result of the work carried out in the framework of the management activities during the first two years can be considered the upload on the EC Participant Portal of a total of 70 out of 70 deliverables (included the OEI Requirement N.4) plus 65 out of 65 internal deliverables produced. The internal deliverables are intended to facilitate the preparation of the official reports; they are uploaded in the EPOS intranet and available for the EC upon request.

Other achievements include the (i) settlement of the governance structure (EPOS internal and external Boards); (ii) definition of common quality procedures; (iii) definition of monitoring strategy and risk management; (iv) establishment of an efficient internal communication flow coherent with the Communication Plan designed in WP2.

Concerning the governance structure, according to the Consortium Agreement, whose content was discussed and distributed during the GA preparation phase and approved and signed by all parties early in October 2015, all beneficiaries have the same rights in the decision-making process. On this purpose the Implementation Phase Council (IPC) has been set down. The IPC usually meet yearly to be informed about the status of the project and discuss, and approve if necessary, issues concerning the consortium (e.g. approve deliverables and amendments). The internal governance structure also includes the Service Coordination Board (SCB), a strategic board composed by the Leaders of WP6-17 and chaired by a person not involved in these WPs, to this board participate, as permanently invited, WP2 and WP3 leaders and the project coordinator. This board discusses issues related to TCS-ICS implementation and interoperability. The Advisory Board, in charge of the external advice and evaluation, is composed by outstanding scientists and IT experts representing global scientific projects/programs as well as by managers from private sector. Specific tasks and duties necessary for the project execution are then assigned to the Project Development Board (PDB) which is chaired by the coordinator and composed by the WP2-7 Leaders and the chairs of the SCB, IPC and BNSR (see below). Issues on a daily basis. The Project Coordinator is of course responsible for the global coordination and organization of all activities and for managing the project at strategic level. The Coordinator is assisted by the Project Director, responsible for the successful delivery of all outputs to guarantee that the project progresses on time and on budget and by the Project Management Office (PMO) composed by skilled staff. The PMO also assists the PDB, SCB, and IPC and in general provides the secretariat for all EPOS IP Boards including the external Boards, namely, *Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR)*, *Board of National Scientific Representatives (BNSR)*, *Ethics Working Group (EWG)*. Finally, with the duty of coordinating the legal establishment of the ERIC, while guaranteeing an effective integration with the EPOS IP project achievements, the *EPOS-ERIC Interim Office* has been established. This office is composed by legal and financial experts and it is led by the project coordinator. During the first two years of the project life, The PMO has organized several face-to-face meetings and teleconference as follows:

- 12 Project Development Board meetings, 5 of those teleconferences
- 3 Implementation Phase Council face to face meetings
- 9 Service Coordination Board meetings, 4 of those teleconferences
- 4 Board of Governmental Representatives face to face meetings
- 2 Board of National Scientific Representatives face to face meetings
- 2 EPOS-ERIC Interim Office face to face meetings
- 3 Ethical Working Group meetings, one of those face to face
- 2 Advisory Board teleconferences (a face to face meeting is scheduled on November the 10th 2017)
- 1 kick-off meeting (on October 2015)
- 2 Integration workshops (on March 2016 and March 2017)
- 1 Annual meeting (on October 2017)
- 1 validation Workshop (on October 2017)

Concerning the **quality control procedures**, a set of procedures, aimed at ensuring the prompt achievement of project objectives, were defined by the PMO and approved by the IPC Members. They mainly affect deliverables quality assessment and the definition of internal reporting procedures. In particular, the deliverables are drafted according to a mandatory standard format provided by the WP2. Furthermore, their approval is subject to a process that varies depending on the deliverable label as 'Key DEL' or 'DEL', being the former the most relevant for IPC decisions. A deliverables check-document in Excel format is also periodically shared with the IPC members on a six-month basis. During the first two years a total of 70 out of 70 deliverables (including OEI Requirement N.4) have been submitted to the EC. Additionally, 65 out of 65 internal deliverables have been also produced. Internal reporting procedures have been identified and summarized in the "*EPOS IP – Reporting Guidelines*" and customized reporting tools, reflecting EC requirements, provided to partners. The PMO ensured a continue support to the partners, on financial, administrative and contractual matters, especially with reference to the Grant Agreement interpretation. The *pre-financing* was distributed to all beneficiaries according to the CA provisions on December 2015. Two *GA amendments* were submitted and approved by the EC, respectively on July 2016 and December 2016. Most important changes were the reallocation of responsibilities within WP10 and the addition of a new beneficiary from November the 1st (M14): Trust-IT (partner n.48) mainly involved in WP2. Suitable shared procedures and templates to facilitate financial and scientific reporting were provided by the PMO and used both the Interim Report M1-9 and for the 1st Periodic Report M1-18. In particular, the PMO drafted three different templates: one for the technical part of the report, based on a simplified version of the inputs required by the EC at WP level; the other consisting in a customized financial reporting tool per partner. The Interim Report M1-9, based on an estimation of costs incurred and activities carried out during the period, was acknowledged as a good exercise in preparation of the first EC Periodic Report. The preparation of the work related to the submission of the First Periodic report M1-18 included the collection and review of all partners' contributions, giving them homogeneity in view of the definition of the technical report; advice and support to partners on costs reporting; verification of the consistency between M1-18 activities and costs; and guidance to the online submission via the Participant Portal.

Concerning the **monitoring strategy**, the PMO developed a risk register, listing all the identified risks per macro categories, a current assessment of the threats they represent to the success of EPOS (likelihood of occurrence and impact), the supervisory Board, the Board/WP Leader responsible for taking appropriate actions, the action decided, and their current status. More details on this issue are reported in Chapter 6 of this document.

An effective **communication strategy** was targeted since the beginning of the project, both internally (among project partners) and externally (towards the EC and any relevant stakeholders). An address book – including partners' contacts divided per role in the project – was drafted and periodically updated by the PMO. Additionally, in view of improving interactions within the project working groups (Boards, WPs, etc.), different mailing lists were created via the intranet system. The EC Project Officers are periodically updated on the project status and promptly informed on any initiative and situations potentially affecting the project work plan, thus providing support in the identification of the best way to proceed. Communication flow among the partnership was addressed as well; daily contacts via emails, phone calls and flash meetings, ensured a smooth running and an efficient coordination of the project activities. Communication towards external stakeholders was specifically addressed by WP2. Further details on communication activities have been provided in paragraph 2.3 of this document.

To analyse the role of women in a large pan-European Research Infrastructure, a Gender Analysis has been performed within EPOS and the results have been presented in various meeting (TCS-ICS Integration Workshop, Prague 2017; *L'Europa è per le donne*, Milan 2017; EGU, Vienna 2017). The analysis has been performed on a sample of 546 users of the EPOS Intranet Platform belonging to different research infrastructures from 25 European countries representing the 47 EPOS IP beneficiaries. Our analysis reveals that over these 546 people participating at various levels in EPOS, only 131 are women. Therefore, the gender balance in EPOS, unfortunately, reflects the general situation of women being outnumbered by men in geosciences research positions. Indeed, most of the women involved in EPOS are active geoscientists (academic or in national research institutes), or have a scientific background. We then analysed in more details the women representation in each EPOS governing and advisory boards, in the transversal WPs, and in the TCS WPs and the outcomes are shown in Figures 7-9. This has allowed us not only to assess the gender balance in a pan-European research infrastructure, but also to investigate how women's participation varies with different aspects of the project implementation (management, coordination, legal, financial or technical).

Figure 7. Governing and Advisory Boards.

Figure 8. Management and transversal WPs.

Figure 9. Thematic Work Packages.

3. MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES

The EPOS Implementation Phase has been designed with the goal of addressing two key challenges: the legal establishment of EPOS-ERIC and the implementation of the Thematic and Integrated Core Services (TCS and ICS) within a coherent delivery framework from technical, legal, governance and financial point of views. The goal of implementing services is mainly addressed within the EPOS IP project, whose concept and work plan have been appropriately organized to successfully achieve the project' objectives. Consequently, the management procedures were designed and planned, already in the EPOS IP project proposal, to tackle the abovementioned key challenges. It is of relevance to read again the Evaluation Summary Report of the EPOS IP project, and in particular the following statement taken from the section Quality and Efficiency of the implementation: *The management structures and procedures are appropriate and build on those developed during the preparatory phase whilst understanding the need for modification to achieve implementation. However, the management structure is complex and parallel activities in EPOS-ERIC and EPOS IP create uncertainty as to areas of responsibility. For example the Board of Government Representatives (BGR) is the decision-making body for EPOS, yet representation by scientific participants is not clear. Similarly, two panels on the Advisory Board is an unnecessary duplication.* After two years of activity in EPOS IP, we can affirm to have addressed these concerns and to have corroborated the efficiency and appropriateness of the management structure and procedures. Figures 2 and 3 of the present report are taken from the EPOS IP proposal and from the Grant Agreement (Description of Activities).

The Board of Governmental Representatives (BGR) is the decision body for the whole EPOS Implementation Phase, thus including both the legal establishment of EPOS-ERIC and the implementation of the EPOS delivery framework. Since the starting of the implementation phase, the BGR is composed by members officially nominated by national ministries to represent national political vision. In turn, the BGR has nominated its internal advisory board, the Board of National Scientific Representatives (BNSR), and is able to nominate its external advisory board at any time. The BNSR has the role of providing scientific and technological advises to BGR for decision-making and for supervising the EPOS IP achievements. The EPOS-ERIC Interim Office at INGV, in synergy with WP1, informs the BGR and the BNSR on the EPOS IP achievements, accomplished through the guidance of the Project Development Board (PDB). This structure and the associated procedures put in place before the beginning of EPOS IP project have proved to be realistic and efficient as corroborated by the important decisions taken by BGR on the ERIC legal establishment and the launching of the EPOS Validation phase at M25. This effective decision-making has been possible because of the efficient management procedure and the effective communication with BGR and BNSR. Following the indications provided in the Project Evaluation Report, the EPOS IP external Advisory Board is composed by a single panel, advising WP1 and PDB on the project progress, impact and success. The distinction between two Advisory Boards (see Figure 2), one for the EPOS IP Project and another for the BGR, has been necessary to avoid conflicts of interest between the management of the EC project and the implementation of the EPOS infrastructure. This decision has been negotiated and subsequently taken in synergy with the BGR.

WP3 under the supervision of PDB and the Project Management Office (PMO) is also collecting all the information necessary to harmonize the EPOS implementation with the national priorities and strategies. WP3 is reporting to BGR through the BNSR about the composition of national Consortia and/or Joint

Research Units formed at national level to join and support the pan-European EPOS implementation. The SCB through WP3 is also monitoring the efforts spent by thematic communities for harmonizing data standardization and quality control among them. Moreover, *WP3 Harmonization* coordinated with *WP1 Management* and *WP2 Communication* is responsible for the Impact assessment of the whole implementation phase to be monitored by the PDB and presented to BGR for approval and decisions.

The Service Coordination Board (SCB) is a component envisioned in the EPOS-ERIC governance model. To foster the implementation of the data and service provision within the 10 TCS participating to EPOS IP, the establishment of the SCB has been anticipated and included in the EPOS IP project work plan. The SCB has the goal of fostering and harmonizing among TCS and with ICS the service implementation and the interoperability for the whole EPOS delivery framework. The SCB is acting as a driver and a facilitator for the solution of issues and bottlenecks emerging during the project lifetime and concerning the implementation of TCS and their interactions with ICS.

The EPOS IP project is managed by *WP1 Management* through the PMO and guided by the Project Development Board (PDB) as depicted in Figure 2. The managerial and operational capacity of WP1 has been strengthened by hiring new personnel ensuring skills, experience and internal organization appropriate to the undertakings (as described in details in the previous chapter). WP1 has coordinated the work of PDB fostering decision-making and the effective guidance of the project. INGV, the hosting institution of the legal seat of the EPOS infrastructure, has also established the EPOS –ERIC Interim Office to support the elaboration of all relevant documents for the legal establishment of EPOS-ERIC (statutes, scientific and technical description, business plan). The coordinated work of the EPOS IP Project Management Office (PMO) and the EPOS–ERIC Interim Office at INGV has allowed to manage the implementation phase keeping on track both the project and the legal establishment of the ERIC.

The Implementation Phase Council (IPC) represents the General Assembly of the project and is committed to govern the management of the Grant Agreement and the commitments with the European Commission. The IPC, being composed by a representative from each beneficiary of the EPOS IP project, is informed about all the achievements and approve the project deliverables. In order to eliminate possible conflicts of roles and uncertainties in responsibility, the IPC members cannot seat in the BNSR.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that the Risk Management Plan has been updated since the beginning of EPOS IP, as it will be discussed in a subsequent section. The Risk Register has been updated on its contents and on critical risks. Moreover, the WPs responsible for Risk Management have been revised. In order to be sure that the Risk Management procedure will be put into practice, the responsibility to monitor and control risk management have been assigned to specific boards or offices: namely, the PDB, the SCB, the BNSR and the EPOS –ERIC Interim Office. This further demonstrates the involvement of these boards in the lifecycle of the implementation phase as well as the effectiveness of their role and responsibility.

The adopted management procedures have been proved to be appropriate in managing the EPOS complexity and effective for these undertakings. This procedure is also reliable and effective to coordinate the *parallel activities in EPOS-ERIC and EPOS IP*. The adopted procedures can eliminate uncertainties in the areas of responsibilities, which are clearly assigned and monitored.

4. COMMITTED RESOURCES

EPOS-IP project has been funded by EC for the implementation phase of EPOS. It will run until September 2019 and produce 125 deliverables aimed at developing the key necessary pieces for the operation of EPOS, including: implementation of the TCS; harmonization and integration with national and European programs; legal, governance and financial frameworks for the TCS and ICS implementation; design and implementation of the ICS platform; and ICS-TCS integration and interoperability. The funding model designed to build the EPOS infrastructure relies on various financial sources, including, but not limited to, the Horizon2020 funding provided by the EC via the EPOS IP project. The EPOS Implementation Phase, composed by the EPOS IP project and the legal establishment of EPOS-ERIC, will guide EPOS toward its operational phase. The EPOS IP project mobilizes an overall budget of 31.030.832€, out of which 18.374.344€ is reimbursed by EU; remaining costs are covered by National Research Organizations participating to the project. The implementation activities require 83% of the budget, Harmonization and Management 12% and 5%, respectively. The Project Management Office oversees the technical, scientific, legal and financial issues of the project, and is in charge for ensuring that EU funding is suitably used to increase RI overall level of performance. On top of the mid-term assessment of the implementation Phase (performed at M24), EPOS IP financial flow alignment to the work plan is periodically monitored, thanks to internal non-official reports at M9, M27, M42 and EC periodic reports at M18, M36 and M48. Reported figures (PMs and costs) are carefully analysed and their consistency with the work plan verified; statistics on the overall trend per partner, WP and activity (e.g. under/over expenditure with respect to the estimated efforts and budget) is regularly provided to the project decisional body (Implementation Phase Council, IPC). The TCS-ICS validation, envisioned in the EPOS IP project between M24 and M36, will allow the assessment of the status of the implementation and the readiness for pre-operation and testing. It will also represent an effective way to monitor and strengthen the overall level of performance of the EPOS infrastructure. In terms of committed resources, two main aspects have to be analysed: the EPOS financial resources and the human resources involved in EPOS.

Regarding the EPOS IP financial resources, the total costs for the period M1-M18 (Figure 10a), corresponded to 11.818. 533,91 €, and the total requested EC contribution for the same period, to 7.137.018,19 €, 39% of the EC contribution for the entire project (Figure 10b). The budget spent during the period M1-M18 corresponded to the 38% over the total requested EC contribution.

Figure 10. Pie charts showing, for the M1-M18 period, the percentage of total costs incurred (a) and the percentage of the total contribution requested to the EC (b).

It is also important to take into consideration the fact that EPOS IP project is 40% co-funded by the EU.

In terms of human resources involved in EPOS IP during the first reporting period (M1-M18), the total Person Months spent corresponds to 39% over the total PM planned for the period M1-M48 (Figure 11a). The PM requested to the EC was 42% over the total (Figure 11b). The personal costs M1-M18, corresponded to 72% of the total cost (Figure 11c).

Figure 11. Pie charts showing, for the period M1-M18, the percentage of person months spent (a), the percentage of Person Months requested to the EC (b), the percentage of personnel costs over the total costs (c).

A projection at M24 suggests that the committed human resources increases due to the number of meetings, initiatives and activities performed in the last 6 months to speed up the service implementation, prepare for the Validation Phase and to perform the technical readiness assessment.

Furthermore, at M30 (March 2018) an Interim Report will be finalized. It will contain the necessary information for the PDB, the IPC and the BNSR to evaluate the state of implementation of the project, the respect of the work plan and whether the project's objectives have been achieved, including an estimation of the financial resources committed in the period M19-27.

5. IMPACT AND EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

EPOS is committed to measure the impact of its implementation phase and the exploitation of results. To undertake this assessment, we are presently finalizing the identification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) taking also advantages of discussions with other research infrastructures (e.g. ELIXIR). Defining performance indicators upfront is required to keep project activities running in the right direction. Indeed, regular monitoring of performance indicators allows wise project management, highlighting the gaps between desired results and measured results provides timely indication of how to progress for closing the gaps. Continuous monitoring enables the project's strategy to adjust to changing needs and to put in place corrective actions in a timely fashion if the trend is not as desired. Therefore, defining suitable Key Performance Indicators is the first step for setting up a monitoring procedure that leads a project towards achieving its desired impacts. The second step will be to actually run the monitoring, but this can be done only starting from the third year of activity (October 2017) when also the validation process will start. Presently, EPOS has identified four categories of KPIs: (i) operation and management (including administration), (ii) communication, (iii) technical performance and (iv) socio-economic, each one containing different KPIs (See Table 2). These KPIs are mainly related to project outputs which are clearly measurable: they provide an objective, quantitative way of assessing the progress of project activities at any point in time and to measure the distance from expected results.

As already stated, final, substantial data for assessing impact will only become available in the later stages of the project, nevertheless, we have performed a first retrospective impact assessment of communication at M23. Indeed, communication is a vector to achieve the full exploitation of results which is a precondition for guaranteeing scientific and socio-economic impact. Accordingly, to secure the project would achieve a satisfactory scientific and socio-economic impact, we must first ensure we are having an impact in terms of communication by constantly evaluating and monitoring our communication activities. The list of EPOS' KPIs adopted to assess communication impact is displayed in Table 3 column 1. The adopted KPIs are suitable to measure the outputs, outgrowth and outcomes of specific communication activities performed through communication tools (e.g. website, intranet, social media) and dedicated events targeted to the EPOS objectives. For each KPI the table indicates the expected outputs by month 24 (30 September 2017), the actual achievement at month 23 (31 August 2017) and an evaluation of the progress status represented by the ratio between the achieved and expected outputs. The fourth column represents the preliminary impact analysis made at M24 (see D2.8 M24 for more details). We have performed such a retrospective analysis having in mind that communication is essential in almost all the other activities undertaken to build the EPOS infrastructure. The legal establishment of EPOS-ERIC, for instance, requires the effective engagement of governments at the highest possible level of engagement corroborated by the approval of key documents for the EPOS sustainability plan. The same is true for the implementation of the ICT functional architecture and for the validation of the EPOS data and service provision. For these reasons we have planned to perform the impact assessment of the EPOS activities through the different groups of dedicated KPIs detailed in Table 2. Subsequently we will adapt specific qualitative indicators to these KPIs to interpret the outgrowth and the outcomes of the communication.

Table 2. Key Performance Indicators, first draft

KPI category		KPIs
Operation and Management		# of countries supporting Step 1 submission of EPOS-ERIC
		# of countries supporting Step 2 committing to EPOS-ERIC
		# of countries having EPOS in national roadmaps
		# of countries/organizations sustaining EPOS operation and the development through in kind-contribution & co-funding
		# of countries/organizations/national data providers making available their resources through the EPOS infrastructure
		# of national/international thematic consortia
		# of service contracts between TCS Service Providers and EPOS-ERIC
Communication (see Table 3)		
Technical Performance	e-Infrastructure related operational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - # of interfaced e-Infrastructures/served e-Infrastructures - # of exploited third-party data repositories and service providers - DDSS
	TCS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - # of DDSS elements and technical maturity - Webservices: *existing*functional*documented - Metadata (Baseline): *available & conformity to baseline*documented - AAI roadmap in place
	ICS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - # of functionalities in GUI level / prioritization - # of functionalities at system level / prioritization - ICS metadata catalogue completeness (qualitative KPI)
	Level of interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping from TCS metadata to baseline (TCS MD to DCAT) - Mapping from baseline to ICS catalogue (DCAT to CERIF)
	Operational Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - # and geographic distribution of accesses /users to data products and services provided by EPOS: *Raw data download (# & type of user / amount and type of data) *Data Products downloads *EPOS Services used *EPOS Software used
	Trans-National Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - # of activities facilitated - # of TNA papers & publications - # of data publications
Socio-Economic		Interaction and impact of EPOS in other EU and global projects
		# of industrial data providers
		# of industrial users
		# of governmental / societal users
		More efficient and effective hazard management (qualitative)
		Risk mitigation through multidisciplinary analysis forecasting hazardous events
		Testimonials on the benefits through EPOS (“success stories”)
# of public engagement events		

Table 3. Key Performance Indicators for communication, including monitoring results, and analysis of communication impact at M23

KPI Category	KPI	Expected outputs	Achieved outputs	Impact assessment	Impact Analysis*	
Communication						
Events organised by EPOS	Scientific events	15	66	440%	High	
	Governmental events	2	12	600%	High	
	Private sector events	4	3	75%	Low	
Events EPOS participated to	Scientific events	30	115	383%	High	
	Governmental events	4	3	75%	Low	
	Private sector events	1	1	100%	expected	
Participation to projects/initiatives	Scientific projects/initiatives within SES	2	2	100%	expected	
	IT projects/initiatives	2	2	100%	expected	
	Other projects/initiatives	2	2	100%	expected	
Outreach	Articles	2	26	130%	High	
	Position Papers	1	1	100%	expected	
	Press Releases	2	2	100%	expected	
	Interviews	10	13	130%	High	
	Brochures / Flyers / etc	20	20	100%	expected	
	Posters	20	36	180%	High	
	Videos	1	2	200%	High	
Website	Unique visitors (weekly avg.)	300	440	146%	High	
Social Media	Twitter					
		Tweets (weekly avg.)	5	12	240%	High
		Followers	300	620	206%	High
	LinkedIn					
		Posts/Updates	20	16	80%	Low
		Community	200	2130	106%	High
	Facebook					
		Contacts	124	290	233%	High
		Likes	124	291	234%	High
	YouTube					
	Channel Subscribers	19	32	168%	High	
	Likes	14	18	128%	High	
Flickr						
	Views	20000	21700	108%	High	
Newsletter	Subscribers	800	1106	138%	High	
	Readers	300	380	126%	High	
Training	Training initiative	15	16	106%	High	
	Trainees	300	705	235%	High	
	People involved in training	12	35	291%	High	
Intranet	Intranet members	300	640	210%	High	
	Sessions	---	16000	---		

* High>100%; expected =100%; Low<100%

The validation phase planned at the third year of the EPOS IP project will provide the necessary information to undertake the impact assessment of the technical performance and infrastructure operation through the KPIs listed in Table 2. In other words, the target value of KPIs and the timeline to get them will be determined by the validation process coordinated by the BNSR and approved by BGR. Moreover, the establishment of user feedback groups in the governance structure of TCS will provide indications and a framework to assess the exploitation of results. This demonstrates the existence of an effective strategy to monitor and assess impact of EPOS IP achievements.

6. UPDATED RISK REGISTER

The EPOS IP project risk management framework has been established to ensure that the project progresses smoothly to the operational phase following the roadmap foreseen by EPOS infrastructure. Therefore, the main aim of risk management is to ensure that project risks are identified and covered by actions so as to eliminate or reduce them, bringing the residual risk to an acceptable level. Regular risk assessment of the project will ensure success in terms of fulfilling project objectives within budget, time and resources available.

Risk identification involves determining which risks or threats are likely to affect the project. Starting from the EPOS roadmap, risk areas have been divided in the following macro categories:

- TCS implementation
 - TCS technical implementation (Data, Data products, Software and Services)
 - TCS financial framework
 - TCS legal and governance
- ICS implementation
- TCS-ICS interoperability
- Harmonization of national strategies
- Communication
- EPOS-ERIC legal establishment

Being risks identified and properly assessed, next step is to put in place a proper risk management plan, entailing the definition of mitigation measures and a contingency plan, and assigning risk responsibilities. All this is summarised in the Risk Register, a frequently updated database detailing all identified risks, including description, probability of occurring, impact on objectives, proposed responses, timescale, contingency plan, WPs/Boards responsible and Supervisory Boards (Table 4). Each risk has been assigned to a WP Leader; the supervision of the risk monitoring is assigned to specific boards to implement mitigation measures for avoiding the risk occurrence, to apply a contingency plan should an adverse event happen. As project activities are carried out and completed, risk factors and events are monitored to determine if trigger events have occurred that would indicate the risk is a reality. Based on trigger events documented during the risk analysis and mitigation processes, the responsible WP/Board will have the authority to put in place day to day risk mitigation activities and/or contingency plans as deemed appropriate (see coloured columns in table 2). The EPOS Risk Register has been released at M12 (D1.2). Here we report a simplified version of the register updated at M24 as a result of the risk monitoring and the application of mitigation measures and contingency plans. The risk register is developed and maintained by the PMO.

Table 4. EPOS Risk Register updated at M24

TCS IMPLEMENTATION						
TCS TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION						
Risk description	Mitigation measures	Contingency Plan	Responsible WP/Board	Supervisory Board	Status M1	Status M24
Fail to validate a sustainable number of DDSS elements to ensure DDSS provision	Effective and shared validation criteria and methodology; check maturity level of DDSS provision from TCS	Foster implementation of DDSS elements included in the roadmap for immature TCS; revise validation criteria and methodology	WP8-17	SCB		Validation methodology, criteria and timeline discussed within communities and approved by BNSR and BGR; the DDSS MT currently contains 369 elements; 133 are ready to be implemented.
Poor contribution from individual TCS to EPOS DDSS provision	Monitor the implementation of DDSS	Revise implementation plan for DDSS elements in the roadmap; monitor activities for TCS components in the roadmap	WP8-17	SCB		The DDSS MT currently contains 369 elements provided by all TCS although an uneven distribution which reflects the nature of each TCS is apparent.
Harmonization working groups fail in the data standardization and quality control	Monitor the activities and achievements of harmonization of WGs	Increase resources and skills dedicated to the harmonization activities	WP6-17	SCB		In total 20 Harmonization Groups (HG) were defined and a Harmonization Matrix prepared outlining the participation to each of these HGs; first level of harmonization was finished by the end of January 2017.
Lack of mature services at the level of NRIs	Foster participative national implementation plans	Ask TCS support to national implementation plans providing experiences, tools and skills	WP8-17	SCB		Currently 133 elements over 369 are declared mature for entering in validation relying on data and services from NRIs.

TCS IMPLEMENTATION						
TCS FINANCIAL FRAMEWORK						
Risk description	Mitigation measures	Contingency Plan	Responsible WP/Board	Supervisory Board	Status M1	Status M24
Fail to receiving financial information from TCS	Provide financial guidelines for TCS cost assessment; support TCS financial work	Exclude TCS from EPOS-ERIC financial plan	WP5	PDB		TCS Cost-Book approved by BGR.
Financial framework failed due to un sustainable implementation costs	Promote sustainability of NRIs at national level; increase host premium for EPOS-ERIC; verify the effectiveness of TCS costs assessment	Exclude TCS from EPOS-ERIC financial plan	PDB	EPOS-ERIC Interim Office		EPOS is already included in the national roadmap of 8 countries, in 16 countries consortia/JRUs has been created to foster a harmonized participation to EPOS; the effectiveness of TCS costs assessment will be check during the validation phase.
TCS LEGAL & GOVERNANCE						
Mismanage of Ethics issues	Establishment of an external Ethics Working Group; Report on Ethics issues	Report the issues to BGR and European Commission	PDB	PMO		Ethics Working Group established; 2 teleconfs and 1 f2f meeting performed; roadmap agreed.
TCS failure to adopt a reliable governance and legal framework	Provide guidance and engage legal expertise within TCS; check Communities engagement	Increase human resorces and skills to support legal and governance; organize specific meetings	WP8-17	PDB		TCS are well advanced in discussing their governance; the engagement of communities is discussed and formalised through Consortium Agreement.
Failure to finalize data policy and access rules	Implement general principles to adapt EPOS data policy and access rules to the heterogeneity of DDSS	Revise data policy and access rules; increase responsibility of TCS	WP3, WP4	PDB		EPOS Data Policy and TNA General Principles discussed and approved by the community and by BGR; adaptation of EPOS data policy to TCS is ongoing.

ICS IMPLEMENTATION						
Risk description	Mitigation measures	Contingency Plan	Responsible WP/Board	Supervisory Board	Status M1	Status M24
Fail to implement ICS portal software	Monitor ICS implementation in WP6-7; Deliver ICS prototype for testing and validation	Acquire new IT resources and skills; revise ICS implementation roadmap	WP7	PDB		First version of the ICS prototype has been delivered in March; a new version is available and it will be tested and validated, during the Validation Phase.
Failure to finalize ICS implementation and associated e-infrastructure	Involve ICS-C hosting institutions in the technical implementation; provide necessary resources and skills to EPOS IT teams	Revise ICS-C architecture; use e-science innovation to validate IT solutions	WP6, WP7	PDB		The ICS-C hosting institutions are fully involved in the technical implementation.
TCS-ICS INTEROPERABILITY						
Fail in adopting a common metadata structure	Organize meetings to foster awareness and readiness within TCS community	Revise metadata structure	WP7	SCB		Common metadata structure discussed and accepted within communities; outcomes must be monitored and assessed during the Validation Phase.
Failure in making TCS interoperable with ICS	Organize TCS-ICS integration meetings; strengthen communication between TCS and ICS development teams	Revise IT solutions and evaluate the possibility to outsource services	WP6, WP7	SCB		Efficient collaborations between TCS and ICS have been put in place; outcomes must be monitored and assessed during the Validation Phase.

HARMONIZATION OF NATIONAL STRATEGIES						
Risk description	Mitigation measures	Contingency Plan	Responsible WP/Board	Supervisory Board	Status M1	Status M24
Failure to engage governments and convince them to prioritize EPOS within their national programs	Foster proactive participation in BGR meetings; effectively engage governments and funding agencies	Organize additional BGR meetings; organize brokerage events in selected Countries	EPOS-ERIC Interim Office	PDB		BGR is very proactive (all meeting attended by 18 countries in average); EPOS in national roadmap of 8 countries.
Fail in engaging broad national representativeness	Foster the establishment of national consortia, Joint Research Units, and engagement of national teams	Organize brokerage events with national communities	WP3	PDB		National consortia and/or JRUs are established in 16 countries,
COMMUNICATION						
Failure to engage users and stakeholders to foster a full exploitation of results	Adopt an effective communication plan; check impact of dissemination and communication activities	Revise communication plan; implement communication tools; strengthen communication activities	WP2	PDB		Users can be efficiently engaged after services are delivered; proper communication actions are in place to keep potential users informed.
Failure of internal and external EPOS communication	Provide tools for internal and external communication; monitor impact of communication via KPIs	Improve communication tools; strengthen awareness and foster use of communication tools	WP2	PDB		Tools for internal and external communication are provided and in use; monitoring of impact of communication via KPIs is in progress.
Failure to demonstrate EPOS impact on science	Engage scientific community; engage Advisory Board to assess impact on science; foster dissemination of EPOS impact	Elaborate an EPOS science plan; emphasize EPOS added value in the Scientific and Technical description	WP3	SCB		A first version of the EPOS White Paper elaborated by the BNSR has been released; the EPOS Scientific and Technical Description has been unanimously approved by BGR.

EPOS-ERIC LEGAL ESTABLISHMENT						
Risk description	Mitigation measures	Contingency Plan	Responsible WP/Board	Supervisory Board	Status M1	Status M24
Failure in integrating ERIC components (ECO and ICS-C)	Negotiate with host countries contributions to host ERIC components	Revise EPOS architecture or selected hosting countries	EPOS-ERIC Interim office	BNSR		The ECO component integration is well established. The ICS-C integration has been discussed with the hosting countries and BGR; due actions ongoing.
Failure to engage countries to support EPOS mission due to: (i) few countries signing the ERIC; (ii) increase of individual membership fees for ERIC	Elaborate an effective EPOS-ERIC financial plan, statutes and scientific and technical description	Further engagement of BGR in EPOS decisions; financial plan revision	EPOS-ERIC Interim Office	BNSR		The EPOS-ERIC financial plan approved by BGR; Statutes and scientific and technical description unanimously approved by BGR; 11 countries have supported the Step 1 submission of EPOS ERIC. Up to 16 are foreseen for the Step 2.

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Following the roadmap envisioned for the EPOS Implementation phase, the first two years of the EPOS IP project have been essentially dedicated to develop the core services (both TCS and ICS) dealing with their sustainability from a technical, legal, governance and financial point of view. The results summarized and discussed in this report corroborate that EPOS IP project is on track respecting the designed workflow and timeline as detailed in the Description of Action. Consequently, the progress achieved in these first two years allows EPOS to now enter into the Validation Phase. This phase has been planned to be dedicated to identify, prioritize and validate data and services (the EPOS data and service provision) ready for the pre-operational and testing phase. EPOS managed to address its first two years goals because:

- the EPOS IP project objectives identified in the project proposal have been actually proved to be relevant and effective to guide the implementation;
- the project concept and the organization of workflow and timeline is appropriate and efficient to ensure the coordination of planned activities;
- the engagement of key stakeholders (data providers, IT experts, National Authorities) is progressing well beyond expectations and it is still increasing after 10 years from the EPOS conception;
- work plan implementation is progressing taking into account and aligning technical, legal, governance and financial point of views;
- the bottom-up approach to prioritize EPOS data and service provision has been successful, as demonstrated by the Technical Readiness Assessment concluded at M24 and by the Validation Phase, launched at M25;
- the engagement of users and other stakeholders (including private sector) is guided by the EPOS communication plan, where key actions, tools and bottlenecks are clearly envisioned;
- risk management has been effective because several key results have been achieved also thanks to mitigation actions and the applications of contingency plans (such as the finalization of the TCS Governance model, the TCS-ICS Cost Book, the cross-TCS Data Harmonization);
- the efficient use of committed resources and the involvement of the proper multi-disciplinary skills for technical, legal, financial and management activities.

The launch of the Validation Phase at M25 is an important milestone of the EPOS IP project. The strategic decision to undertake a Technical Readiness Assessment between M18 and M24 has been crucial for identifying, through an internal bottom up approach, the data, data-products and services (DDSS elements) ready to enter into the Validation Phase. In turn, the validation of EPOS core services (both at the TCS and ICS level) will speed up activities concerning the current challenges of implementing a user strategy and the data management plan. Importantly and strategically, the validation process relies on both, a bottom up approach to implement the TCS Governance and DDSS provision and a top down assessment of the success rate in implementing core services. This will yield a shared prioritization and a viable sustainability of the EPOS data and service provision.

The roadmap envisioned for the EPOS Implementation phase includes making progress toward the legal establishment of EPOS ERIC. The EPOS IP project has helped in achieving important results to ensure such a progress by:

- producing the TCS Cost Book, a fundamental ingredient of the EPOS Business Plan;

- making the TCS structure coherent with the governance of EPOS-ERIC from a legal point of view;
- adopting General Principles for Data Policy and Access Rules that are coherent with EPOS-ERIC vision and mission;
- identifying the data and service provision (DDSS Master Table) and the strategies to prioritize services to be validated before the pre-operational and testing phase;
- developing the ICS Central Hub coherently with the EPOS-ERIC governance, legal and financial model;
- ensuring the technical implementation of the ICS Central Hub prototype to be delivered to the hosting countries for production during the operational phase guided by EPOS-ERIC;
- coordinating harmonization activities with national priorities;
- coordinating communication activities relying on a shared Communication Plan;
- managing the EPOS IP project coherently with indications coming from the European Commission, ESFRI and National Governments.

The consciousness of the achieved results and the knowledge of the EPOS implementation roadmap allow the identification of the following current challenges to face and/or bottlenecks to overcome:

- ensure long-term sustainability for the EPOS data and service provision,
- secure the operation of a successful ICT functional architecture which guarantees interoperability and user interface,
- implementation of the User Strategy,
- launch of the EPOS Training Plan,
- effective impact assessment including socio-economic impact,
- implementation of collaborative frameworks with the private sector.

EPOS is working to demonstrate its added value as a platform toward innovation for delivering relevant scientific research outputs for science and society. There is the concrete possibility to unlock the innovation potential of EPOS in terms of effective contributions and solutions to (i) data interoperability and data science, (ii) societal benefits by sharing new products and scientific information, (iii) hazard assessment and risk mitigation by delivering new products and services at pan-European level harmonized with national policies, (iv) safe and sustainable exploitation of geo-resources. The progress achieved so far is also concerning the assessment of EPOS scientific impact and science case consisting of: (i) access for scientists, young researcher and students to services for using and interpreting multidisciplinary data and facilities from solid Earth science; (ii) fostering technological innovation to collect new observations and measurements of Earth dynamics; (iii) integrating in-situ and satellite Earth observations to understand natural phenomena (e.g. earthquakes, volcano eruptions and unrest episodes, tsunamis, landslides) as well as man-induced phenomena and anthropogenic hazard; (iv) disseminating solid Earth scientific progress to society to foster a better understanding of the environment and geo-hazards.

EPOS is presently halfway through its implementation phase. Achieved results and the effective planning of activities guarantees that a significant progress has been made toward EPOS construction and operation.